

22NRM03 “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling for heavy duty hydrogen transport”

Report A3.3.2/A3.3.3

Definition of the parameters, the equipment needed, and the requirements for safety and venting needed for the development of a real-size metrological validation facility for HD-HRS

Identification of barriers which need to be addressed for the construction of the validation facility

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Summary

MetHyTrucks aims to propose a recommendation for the development of a real-size metrological validation facility for sampling devices at HD-HRS. This document aims to collect the parameters to be tested, the equipment needed, and the requirements for safety and venting needed for such a facility. This document also addresses technical aspects regarding the accurate contamination of hydrogen in such facilities, how to monitor the contaminated hydrogen and how to remove the contamination from the facility (cleaning process). However, it is also clear that such a platform will be very expensive to build and maintain, and this effort should be weighed against the outcomes that this will bring. Preferably, the overall system should be simplified as much as possible without compromising the testing.

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Parameters that should be assessed at a future facility	5
2.1 Bias/Recovery yields	5
2.2 False positives	6
2.3 Precision	6
2.4 Time dependency / test-retest	6
3 Validation principles	6
3. Equipment needed at the test platform designed for validation of sampling systems	7
3.1 Supply and storage of hydrogen including possible method to accurately contaminate the hydrogen	8
3.2 Dispenser	9
3.3 Controlled parameters	9
3.4 Equipment for venting	9
3.5 Mocking tank	9
3.6 Analytical measurement facility	10
3.7 Monitoring equipment	10
3.8 Cleaning of the station	10
4. Requirements to ensure safe utilization of real size metrological validation facility for sampling devices at HD-HRS	11
4.1 Risk assessment	11
4.2 Staff	12
4.3 Venting	12
5. Conclusion	12
6. Bibliography	13
7. Annex 1 – Hydrogen tanks	14

1. Introduction

Hydrogen quality is crucial for the performance and lifetime of hydrogen fuel cells, as even trace level contamination can be damaging for some of the components of the fuel cell or critical to the system (an example here is the potential negative effect of water during the pre-cooling). Reliable and traceable purity measurements can only be obtained if the sample collected is representative of the hydrogen dispensed at the HRS. During the project MetHyTrucks, several sampling devices are being developed specifically for HD HRS. However, to ensure their correct function and the correct function of any sampling device developed in the future, a proper validation is required. This implies gathering specific rigorous evidence that demonstrates that the sample collected by the device is representative of the hydrogen delivered at the HRS. Understanding the behaviour of all relevant contaminants in sampling conditions is complicated experimentally as it requires to test for their absence (avoiding air leak) and for their presence (yield of recovery). In theory, sampling validation would preferably be done at the nozzle of an existing HRS. Validating the absence of contamination is often feasible as most HRS should dispense hydrogen with a purity of at least 99.97%. The biggest issue when validating any sampling system relates to the need to carefully select an HRS where these comparisons/validations will be performed. If the gas dispensed is fully compliant with the quality standards (i.e. impurity levels below the ISO 14687 threshold levels), then the information obtained on the sampling device will provide very limited information (mostly when the limit of quantification of the methods used is close to the threshold levels), especially regarding recoveries. An exception would be if the analytical methods used have an extremely low detection limit (typically nmol/mol to picomol/mol) which is often not possible in most laboratories. Secondly, it would require that the hydrogen delivered at an HRS has a very stable and well-defined quality for all compounds to avoid variation of fuel quality during the validation testing. Another possibility will be to validate the sampling methodologies in a controlled environment where hydrogen is contaminated with known amounts of one or more relevant impurities. While being potentially easier to implement for some reactive compounds, a controlled environment such as a laboratory may differ from HRS operation in terms of flow, pressure or temperature. Therefore, it may not fully represent the sampling at the nozzle of an HRS.

Another aspect with validated sampling systems is that it provides conditions to determine uncertainties due to sampling.

The optimal option for validation and thereafter uncertainty determination must be to conduct the tests at facilities such as a test platform designed and constructed to test different aspects related to the production, storage, distribution of hydrogen or laboratory-based (for flexibility in parameter control and gas composition) provided that accurate gas contamination can be prepared to further validate methodologies.

Several test platforms already exist to study different aspects of the refuelling. These stations have been described in the report produced from the activity A3.3.1 [1] of MetHyTrucks. However, for technical reasons, most operators of living test platforms are reluctant to use contaminated hydrogen. Therefore, MetHyTrucks aims to propose a recommendation for the development of a real size metrological validation facility for sampling devices at HD-HRS. This document aims to collect the parameters to be tested, the equipment needed, and the requirements for safety and venting needed for such a facility. This document also addresses technical aspects regarding the accurate contamination of hydrogen in such facilities, how to monitor the contaminated hydrogen and how to remove the contamination from the facility (cleaning process).

2. Parameters that should be assessed at a future facility

The validation exercise shall demonstrate that the sampling systems are fit-for-purpose. However, these validation exercises are time-consuming and very expensive (they require a lot of preparation time, including risk assessment as well as expensive analyses), compromises may be needed; for example, validation will be done at only one set of parameters (flow, pressure, temperature) and it is assumed that the results of the validation exercises are also applicable for other conditions.

Regarding measurement of uncertainties, there are two main sources contributing to the uncertainty associated with sampling that need to be determined:

- 1) Random errors arising from the sampling (called **sampling precision**) can be obtained from repeated sampling – need to be done from the same storage bank or storage banks with similar quality of hydrogen
- 2) Systematic errors arising from the sampling (called **sampling bias**); can be obtained from recovery yields test

2.1 Bias/Recovery yields

One of the main parameters to demonstrate this is the recovery yield, which is estimated by comparing the known amount fraction of impurities in hydrogen dispensed at an HRS to the values obtained from the analysis of the hydrogen sampled by the sampling system. It serves as a measure of the technique's effectiveness, reflecting the retrieval efficiency of an analyte. For accurate assessments, the percent recovery values are ideally near 100%. This implies that the quality of the hydrogen used to determine recovery yields is known and stable but also that the hydrogen contains all or many of all impurities to be analysed according to ISO 14687:2025 [2] and EN 17124:2022 [3].

The terms “trueness”, “recovery” and “bias” are often used interchangeably and therefore complementary terms that both refer to the difference between the true value and the average value.

Trueness: Closeness of the agreement between the average value obtained from a large series of test results and an accepted reference value.

Bias: The difference between the limiting mean and the true value.

Recovery is often used and is usually defined as $1 - \text{bias}$ (i.e., a recovery of 80% corresponds to a bias of 20%).

To estimate the systematic bias, some tools are proposed in the Nordtest NT TR 604 guide [4]: reference sampling target, sampling proficiency testing schemes, inter-method comparisons, known value of sampling target, reference sampling procedure.

If this bias cannot be estimated, it can be considered that:

$u_{\text{sampling}} = s_{r, \text{sampling}}$ Where $s_{r, \text{sampling}}$ is the repeatability for the sampling

2.2 False positives

Similarly, as for recovery yields, false positives may be evaluated by comparing the known amount fraction of impurities in hydrogen dispensed at an HRS to the values obtained from the analysis of the hydrogen sampled by the sampling system, but they can also be evaluated using a very clean hydrogen and are specifically relevant for oxygen, nitrogen and water (sign of air contamination). Eventually, the results obtained with pure hydrogen may be used to correct bias when working on real hydrogen samples.

2.3 Precision

Repeated sampling is recommended in order to evaluate the uncertainty contributions due to the sampling, in particular random errors arising from the sampling. The calculation of the contribution of the sampling is, however, complex. The simplest method, called the duplicates method, requires repeating the same nominal sampling protocol. Each duplicate is then analysed twice.

To avoid drawing false conclusions, it is important to ensure that the systems that will be validated or compared use the same quality/source of hydrogen, so it is preferable that the systems are tested using the same storage bank, which is not always possible to do practically (see Table 1). However, it is not also simple to Another precaution is to control the variable parameters as much as technically possible.

2.4 Time dependency / test-retest

While repeatability is the ability to reproduce the same result under identical conditions, time dependency is to be considered if changes in the hydrogen quality are expected over time. This could be the case for a hydrogen containing sticky impurities. The concentration of "hydrogen-containing sticky impurities" can fluctuate over time due to changes in surface properties, where the process of passivation (making a surface less reactive) can decrease/increase their presence. Test-retest can be used to assess the consistency of a sampling system when repeating the same test on the same sample of hydrogen at a different point in time. These tests can only be done when measuring a composition expected to stay constant in the sample taken.

3 Validation principles

Table 1 taken from A3.2.2 [5] of MetHyTrucks gives indication on how the parameters at the HRS station can be set so the conditions applied to systems to be compared are as similar as possible. This information is also relevant for a future development of a real size metrological validation facility for sampling devices at HD-HRS.

Table 1 – Overview of the parameters to be used during the different validation exercises

	Validation by comparison			
	Only parallel sampling systems (all HD or all LD)	Only direct sampling systems (all HD or all LD)	Parallel and direct sampling systems (all HD or all LD) (MHV2)	LD and HD sampling systems
Mode	Using refuelling protocol	Manual	Combination manual and refuelling protocol	Manual or using refuelling protocol
Refuelling protocol	SAE J2601-5 Wenger protocol (MCF-HF-G)	None / manual mode, set pressure	SAE J2601-5 None for direct	
Nozzle	WEH TK16 HF & WEH TK17	use universal receptacle (e.g., WEH TK17-H2-35MPa-ENR)	use universal receptacle (e.g., WEH TK17-H2-35MPa-ENR)	HRS with receptacle compatible with HD and LD or universal receptacle (e.g., WEH TK17-H2-35MPa-ENR)
Flow	Defined by the protocol (applied only to the max flow as actual flow varies (vehicle dependent))	Regulated by the hardware and the cylinder but interesting to measure what flow was realized	Defined by protocol or regulated by hardware	Max 60 g/s
Starting temperature	To be set (for ex. -20 °C)	To be set (for ex. -20 °C)	Set temperature for manual mode	To be set (for ex. -20 °C)
Pressure	To be set (350 better option than 700 bar)	350 bar	350 bar (HD) 700 bar (LD)	350 bar
Storage bank	To be set so all systems tested receive the same gas (check that there is enough gas)		Define 1 storage bank for the two realisations	Defined storage bank to ensure LD and HD sample a similar % of the storage bank (if more than 1)
Installation	Sampling systems connected in series	Back-to-back to minimize risks for changes but manage risks that one sampler does not affect the other	Back-to-back refueling to minimize risks for changes but manage risks that one sampler affects the other	Back-to-back refueling to minimize risks for changes but manage risks that one sampler affects the other

3. Equipment needed at the test platform designed for validation of sampling systems

Ideally, the test platform should consist of an HRS (which allows control of parameters such as flow, pressure, temperature, refuelling protocols...), a point of contamination of the hydrogen and monitoring possibilities to check the composition of the contaminated hydrogen close to the point where the sampling systems will be tested.

3.1 Supply and storage of hydrogen including possible method to accurately contaminate the hydrogen

The platform should have a production of hydrogen and hydrogen storage. One method of contamination could be to depressurize the high-pressure storage to below 10 MPa, use a primary gas reference materials (PRMs) to spike the hydrogen and repressurize the storage using onsite hydrogen (produced or delivered). It would create in the high-pressure storage a known spiked hydrogen fuel (mass of spiked CRM added and volume and pressure of the hydrogen in the high-pressure storage to determine the dilution yield).

The validation of the sampling system should then be done using only gas flow from the high-pressure storage to avoid further dilution. Verification of the composition through sampling of the storage tank is recommended. For reactive compounds, the time dependency between the contamination and the sampling validation is critical and may require preliminary study to define it.

Some drawings representing how the contamination can be implemented are shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Schematic of how to contaminate hydrogen fuel within one storage bank. The step A-B-C follows the process proposed to ensure the hydrogen fuel is spiked accurately for sampling validation.

The selection of the hydrogen storage tank may impact the type of composition achieved and reactive stability. A system to vent the contaminated hydrogen or use it in alternative application (combustion or stationary fuel cell) may be relevant to limit the venting of excess spiked hydrogen fuel.

It is technically difficult to produce a contaminated hydrogen containing all the regulated impurities (several challenges: reactivity between species, treatment of the cylinder optimal for some species and

not for others....). An alternative would be to select a reasonable number of representative impurities. For example, the hydrogen could be contaminated with one representative for these different groups:

1. Tracers (inert, no impact)
2. Sticky
3. Reactive

Studies to produce accurately contaminated hydrogen has been conducted in previous projects (MetroHyVe1 and MetroHyVe2 for example). Contaminated hydrogen has been successfully produced for the different intercomparisons that have been organised for the projects MetroHyVe1 (CO, N₂, H₂O in one cylinder and H₂S in another), MetroHyVe2 (He, Ar, N₂, CO₂, CH₄, C₂H₆, CO, C₂H₆S in one cylinder) and in HyQuality Hydrogen Europe (all 14 specified gaseous compounds, but in two different cylinders; Ar, formic acid, formaldehyde and H₂S in one of these cylinders).

3.2 Dispenser

A future real-size metrological validation facility for sampling devices at HD-HRS should have at least a dispenser to deliver the hydrogen which is equipped with nozzles for H35 and H70 refueling (WEH TK17-H2-35MPa-ENR and WEH TK16 HF).

3.3 Controlled parameters

Ideally, a future real size metrological validation facility for sampling devices at HD-HRS should offer the flexibility to configure different set of refueling parameters for the flow, the pressure, and temperature) including the possibility to apply different refueling protocols, to select a specific bank, and to work in manual mode.

3.4 Equipment for venting

A future real size metrological validation facility for sampling devices at HD-HRS should have an infrastructure with standardised vent connections (for example, connections can be ½ inches but there is currently no standard size) which can be used to fulfil the requirements for venting and purging of the sampling devices to be tested. A discussion of the volume and flow to be vented must be conducted before any test (see 4.3).

It should also have space for the installation of mobile vents that may be used in some sampling strategies. Report A1.5.1 which reviews the safety and venting requirements for the different hydrogen sampling strategies (direct, parallel) can be used as a guideline for the dimensional requirements for HD vents (each sampling system having its own requirements). An example for vent dimension is the vent mast used by ENGIE, 5 m height with an inner diameter of around 2,3 - 2,5 cm and an outer diameter of 2,54 cm.

3.5 Mocking tank

A mocking tank can be useful in some cases when testing sampling systems using the series sampling strategy especially if the spiked hydrogen fuel could harm a FCEV. In that case, Type IV tanks (see Annex 1) are probably the best option.

However, some considerations must be taken into account. If the sampling system required a representative HDV volume, how to handle the contaminated hydrogen used to fill the mocking tank. Are there specific environmental or safety aspect to consider.

If the system requires a smaller tank: what is the impact on the representativity of the sampling.

3.6 Analytical measurement facility

Validation of a sampling system requires analysis of the hydrogen collected according to the quality standards (ISO 14687 and EN 17124). To avoid introducing random or systematic errors due to the analysis, all samples are preferably analysed at one facility. It could be onsite, which simplifies transport of the samples, or offsite if onsite analysis is not possible. No matter the choice, the laboratory must have demonstrated analytical capabilities for hydrogen purity assessment (through validation, accreditation or participation in intercomparison analysis exercise).

3.7 Monitoring equipment

As the contamination of the hydrogen is most likely to be realised in the storage, monitoring equipment is very important to control the quality of the hydrogen that will actually reach the sampling device. It is likely that some loss can occur in the different stages from the storage to the nozzle.

The position of the monitoring equipment is challenging; there are three main options:

- Preferably the monitoring equipment is placed as close as possible to the point where the sampling device will be tested using a bleed. However, the change in pressure, temperature, flow in the system will be very challenging to manage for the implementation of any monitoring instrument
- The monitoring equipment can be placed after a sampling device, but this sampling device must be fully validated first

Monitoring at the high-pressure storage tank which can be contaminated. The pressure and flow can be managed easily for the online analyser but the hydrogen gas will not exactly represent the gas sampled as several steps happening further down in the process such as precooling and compression may affect some compounds as water or reactive species as sulphur.

The installation could include online instruments or sensors that have been validated prior to the implementation to analyse continuously components. These data can be useful to check the composition of the hydrogen being sampled. In that case, the platform will also require specific equipment to calibrate the online instruments.

Finally, it is also likely that some impurities cannot be analysed as online instruments are not yet available/reliable for those impurities or cannot meet the LOQ requirements.

3.8 Cleaning of the station

If sampling systems shall be tested using both pure hydrogen and contaminated hydrogen, it is necessary to ensure that the whole system can be fully cleaned. Cleaning can be done by purging all equipment and processes that have been in contact with contaminated hydrogen with pure hydrogen until all

impurities have been quantitatively removed. It could be necessary to first evaluate how much cleaned hydrogen must be flowed through the system in order to quantitatively removed the contamination. The cleaning process is also preferably monitored with adequate online analysers.

Another aspect to consider is how to handle the contaminated hydrogen during the cleaning process. Here again, are there specific environmental or safety aspect to consider?

4. Requirements to ensure safe utilization of real size metrological validation facility for sampling devices at HD-HRS

The sampling of hydrogen fuel at HRS is an operation within an explosive atmosphere area involving safety risks. Sampling devices may require venting of hydrogen prior, during and after the sampling. In many cases, the sampling systems need to be purged several times with large volumes of hydrogen or at various locations of the sampling system. Therefore, an important aspect to consider is how to safely perform hydrogen venting at an HRS during a sampling event (e.g. ATEX zoning, flow, pressure, height, authorisation). For safety reason, H2 leak sensors should be installed in relevant places according to adequate guidelines.

4.1 Risk assessment

Each experiment to be conducted at the future real size metrological validation facility for sampling devices at HD-HRS shall be prepared and extensively described in an experimental plan which also includes a dedicated risk assessment for each experiment.

An example of experimental plan is given in the Figure 2 (taken from the first experimental campaign done in MetHyTrucks).

Figure 2. Example of experimental plan

Description	Sampling system	Sampling type	pressure line	Protocol	Parameters				Flow metering	Scope	Analysis			
					Precooling	Manual pressure setting	Initial pressure	Pressure sink			Storage bank	Implementation	H2 demand [kg]	
Sampling of Bank 4 + 5											ZBT & NPL			
Sampling of Bank 7											ZBT & NPL			
Sampling of pressure sink (350 l tank)											ZBT & NPL			
Functionality test & protocol testing	Hy-SaM	Parallel	35 MPa HF	SAE J2601-5 (MFC-HF-G)	T20 (HX)	-	manually set PRR (according to SAE J2601-1)	5 MPa	350 l	Medium Pressure (4+5)	no	Full analysis?	ZBT, NPL	1.5
Functionality test & comparison of sampling systems	ENGIE system	Direct	35 MPa HF	SAE J2601-1	T20 (HX)	-	SAE J2601-1	?	55 l	Medium Pressure (4+5)	no	Full analysis?	NPL and ENGIE (if sufficient gas)	2
Functionality test & comparison of sampling systems	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	T20 (HX)	-	Manually set pressure at HRS	-	-	Medium Pressure (4+5)	no	Full analysis?	NPL	1
Functionality & flow metering (with primary standard)	Hy-SaM	Parallel	35 MPa HF	-	T20 (HX)	-	SAE J2601-1	?	200 l	Medium Pressure (4+5)	yes	Full analysis?	ZBT, NPL	5
Repetition Test 4	Hy-SaM	Parallel	35 MPa HF	-	T20	-	SAE J2601-1	?	300 l	Medium Pressure (4+5)	yes	Full analysis?	ZBT, NPL	
Functionality & flow metering	ENGIE system	Direct	35 MPa HF	-	T20	-	manually set PRR	?	55 l	Medium Pressure (4+5)	yes	Full analysis?	NPL	1
Functionality & flow metering	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	T20 (HX)	-	manually set PRR	-	-	Medium Pressure (4+5)	yes	Full analysis?	NPL	1
Repetition test 1	Hy-SaM	Parallel	35 MPa HF	SAE J2601-5 (MFC-HF-G)	T20 (HX)	-	manually set PRR (according to SAE J2601-1)	5 MPa	350 l	Medium Pressure (4+5)	no	Full analysis?	ZBT, NPL	1.5
Repetition Test 2	ENGIE system	Direct	35 MPa HF	SAE J2601-1	T20 (HX)	-	SAE J2601-1	?	55 l	Medium Pressure (4+5)	no	Full analysis?	NPL and ENGIE (if suffic) 2 kg	
Repetition Test 3	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	T20 (HX)	-	Manually set pressure at HRS	-	-	Medium Pressure (4+5)	no	Full analysis?	NPL	1
Particulate testing & Protocol testing?	HDHC & HySaM	Direct	70 MPa	Maintenance	ambient?	-	-	-	-	H2O, N2	?		ZBT	
Direct sampling temperature tests	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	ambient	35 MPa	-	-	-	Medium Pressure (4)	no	H2O	NPL	1
Direct sampling temperature tests	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	T10 (Alu-Block)	35 MPa	-	-	-	Medium Pressure (4)	no	H2O	NPL	1
Direct sampling temperature tests	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	T20	35 MPa	-	-	-	Medium Pressure (4)	no	H2O	NPL	1
Direct sampling temperature tests	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	T30	35 MPa	-	-	-	Medium Pressure (4)	no	H2O	NPL	1
Direct sampling temperature tests	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	T40	35 MPa	-	-	-	Medium Pressure (4)	no	H2O	NPL	1
Direct sampling pressure tests – defined by protocol (1)	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	?	?	-	-	-	-	-	no	Full analysis?	NPL	1
Direct sampling pressure tests (2)	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	ambient	6,9 MPa	-	-	-	Medium Pressure (4)	no	Full analysis?	NPL	1
Direct sampling pressure tests (3)	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	ambient	20 MPa	-	-	-	Medium Pressure (4)	no	Full analysis?	NPL	1
Direct sampling pressure tests (4)	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	ambient	35 MPa	-	-	-	Medium Pressure (5)	no	Full analysis?	NPL	1
Direct sampling pressure tests	NPL HD direct system	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	ambient	6,9 MPa	-	-	-	Medium Pressure (5)	no	Full analysis?	NPL	1

As an example, if the facility is located in France, an initial exhausted safety study has to be carried out before the commissioning of the installation, this includes:

- HAZOP (HAZard and Operability) study
- HAZID (HAZard IDentification) study
- ATEX study with risk scenario modelling

These studies are normally done for a fixed process and need to be adapted in the case where different sampling devices will be connected to the process. In this particular case, a general use case needs first to be defined and studied during the initial safety studies. Then, before each sampling device testing, an evaluation of the differences between the use case and the particular configuration needs to be performed. If the variations are minors and don't affect the risk scenario, the sampling can be performed otherwise, a specific risk analysis needs to be performed. These steps are time consuming and must involve experts on safety which increase the cost of a sampling kit evaluation.

4.2 Staff

Only trained staff should use the real size metrological validation facility for sampling devices at HD-HRS.

4.3 Venting

A future facility will have to consider how venting can be performed when testing any sampling device. Currently, the requirements for venting differ upon the design of the sampling systems. Hydrogen sampling systems have their own venting strategies (e.g., portable vent), which are developed specifically for each device. For example, some devices require a purge, others are designed to function without. Some systems use the vent of the HRS while others need a venting stack.

The venting requirement shall be discussed prior to testing, and the feasibility must be checked beforehand (need for connection to the HRS infrastructure, volume to be vented, installation of mobile vents...)

However, it would be interesting to propose a standalone design at the facility that could accommodate most of the sampling devices. The installation should therefore preferably include multiple vent masts using a burner and any sampling system should be connected to this installation.

Another aspect to consider is the current and future requirements regarding the release of hydrogen in atmosphere or the safety concern when using a mobile mast. The installation should implement multiple vent masts using burners and the sampling system needs to be connected at this installation.

Another option may be to capture the hydrogen released during venting for use to generate energy (e.g., metal hydride capture, use for backup power). This may not be feasible for sampling kit validation due to connection compatibility, but it can be used during HRS cleaning or venting steps related to change of hydrogen contaminant composition in the storage.

5. Conclusion

The optimal option for validation and thereafter uncertainty determination is to conduct tests at an HRS providing accurately contaminated hydrogen. Ideally, the test platform should consist of an HRS (which

allows control of parameters such as flow, pressure, temperature, refuelling protocols...), a point of contamination of the hydrogen and monitoring possibilities to check that the composition of the contaminated hydrogen close to the point where the sampling systems will be tested. However, the implementation of monitoring equipment is challenging. Placed before the sampling devices, the change in pressure, temperature, flow in the system will be very challenging to manage. Placed after the sampling device, it requires that this sampling device has first been fully validated.

It is also clear that such a platform will be very expensive to build and maintain, and this effort should be weighed against the outcomes that this will bring. Preferably, the overall system should be simplified as much as possible without compromising the testing. Validation in a more controlled environment is also a more economical approach.

6. Bibliography

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7. Annex 1 – Hydrogen tanks

Common methods for on-board hydrogen storage include liquid hydrogen storage, compressed gas storage and material-based storage (metal hydrides). Current hydrogen vehicles are mostly equipped with a compressed hydrogen gas system, which stores compressed hydrogen gas in hydrogen tanks.

There are generally five types of hydrogen tanks, which differ in the materials used, although only Type III and IV tanks are used in vehicles.

Type I hydrogen cylinders are made entirely of metal. Common metals used are steel and aluminium alloys. These hydrogen tanks are the simplest of the five types to manufacture and are therefore the cheapest. They can be manufactured in a very wide range of capacities and the working pressure is usually a few hundred bar. Due to the high density and required wall thickness of the metal, Type I tanks are heavy and are primarily used for stationary applications such as large-scale industrial hydrogen storage. **Type II** hydrogen tanks are also all-metal cylinders, similar to Type I, except that they are reinforced with carbon or glass filaments wrapped around the straight body portion. These tanks are also used for stationary applications, and the working pressure is in the same range as Type I tanks but often slightly higher due to the additional high strength wrapping.

Type III and IV hydrogen cylinders are fully wrapped in composite material, usually carbon fibre. The difference between Type III and Type IV is that the former uses a metallic liner and the latter a polymeric liner. Both types are used in the automotive industry due to the significant weight savings compared to Type I and II. In this case, the thicker outer composite layer acts as the main load-bearing component and the thin liner layer acts as the sealing layer. Due to their higher strength and lower density, both Type III and Type IV tanks allow higher internal pressures than other types, and the overall weight and wall thickness of the tanks are significantly lower. This allows the hydrogen gas to be compressed to a higher density and more gas to be carried in smaller and lighter tanks.

Type V tanks are made entirely of composite materials. They are even lighter than Type IV tanks and can withstand even higher pressures. However, Type V tanks are still under development and are expensive to produce.

For a working pressure of 350 bar, Type III tanks are usually used because the cost is much lower than for Type IV tanks. Of course, the same mass of stored hydrogen at 350 bar requires a larger tank than at 700 bar. Therefore, 350 bar tanks are more commonly used for heavy duty vehicles (buses, trucks) where space is not an issue and several large tanks can be installed.

The installation of several large tanks is not suitable for passenger cars, where space is usually limited. Type IV cylinders with a working pressure of 700 bar are mainly used here.

For example:

@350 bar / 20 °C: $23.65 \text{ kg/m}^3 = 0.02365 \text{ kg/L}$ (0.02365 kg stored hydrogen per Liter)

@700 bar / 20 °C: $39.69 \text{ kg/m}^3 = 0.03969 \text{ kg/L}$ (0.03969 kg stored hydrogen per Liter)

That means a tank for 5 kg hydrogen has a size of 126.0 L (700 bar) or 211.5 L (350 bar), respectively. Consequently, a 350 bar tank must be 1.67 times larger than a 700 bar tank to store the same amount (mass) of hydrogen.